

AN ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM IN INDIA : ISSUES AND CHALLENGES AND A WAY FORWARD

Areeba Khan¹ Noria Farooqui²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Management School of Management
and Business studies Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi, 110062

²Assistant Professor, Department of Business Management,
School of Management and Business Studies, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi-110062

INTRODUCTION

Genesis

The concept of Public Distribution System in the country was evolved around 1942 due to shortage of foodgrains during 2nd World War and Government intervention in distribution of food started. This intervention of Government in distribution of foodgrains in the food scarcity period and, thereafter, continued in major cities, towns & certain food deficit areas. This policy of Public Distribution System/Rationing System has undergone several changes with every lap of Five Year Planning System in the country. The Seventh Five Year Plan assigned to it a crucial role by bringing the entire population under Public Distribution System and became a permanent feature in the country's economy. The aim of the Indian Food Security Policy is to make food grains available to the public at a fair price. Therefore, the objectives are (i) the provision of sufficient or adequate food grain supply and (ii) the distribution of food grains at an affordable price. In the country after the Second World War the method of public distribution strives to achieve certain twin aims. In Government of India's view, the PDS aspires to safeguard the consumers from the effects of rising prices and keep the nutritional status of our people at appropriate levels. The PDS supplies stabilize the open market prices, mitigating scarcity and deterring speculative impulses by increasing supply.

Kautilya 'Arthashastra' is the root of food security through PDS. In his study on the approaches of neutralizing the consequences of famine, he proposes the following:

- Disseminate royal store seeds and food to the public in concessional terms.
- Start food-for-work projects such as constructing Forts or irrigation works.
- Distribute stocks of royal food.
- Commandeer, private food stocks for public dissemination.
- Seek assistance from friendly kings.

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- Temporary transfer of the affected population to another region.
- Promote relocation to other countries (temporary).
- Transfer the entire population (along with the King and Court). to a region or land with plenty of harvests or close to sea, lakes, or rivers.
- Complement harvest by surplus cultivation of cereals, vegetables, fruits, by fishing, and hunting wild animals, birds and cattle.

Social protection was both a private and a state affair in Kautilya. The family leader was primarily responsible for the maintenance of the family including- parents, children, wife, minor brothers and unmarried or widowed children; without first supplying his wife and children, nobody could be made an ascetic. The government was nevertheless obligated to have a safety net and protect children, elderly, children less and vulnerable people.

The history behind the establishment in India of the PDS is entrenched in starvation and food shortages under India's British colonial rule. Almost million people died in the - 17 - Bengal famine in 1770, which was basically the outcome of loot by the colonizers of East India Company. Twenty big famines and scarcities took place between 1860 and 1910. The Bengal famine of 1943 was the last famine in British India.

In 1858 the East India Company came to an end after which several committees came out with reports on British India. The Baird Smith report of the famine 1860-61, 1880 report of the Commission of Famine, then the implementation of famine codes, the report of the Commission of Famine in 1896-97 on famines, the report of the Commission of Famine on famines 1899-1900, and the report of the Committee of Famine on famine in Bengal 1945 (17). 'The backbone of the famine relief strategy embodied in the Famine Codes was the organization of massive public works'.

The food shortages during World War II and the Bengal Famine of 1943, was followed by the post-independence Indian farming. Public involvement was actually related to food shortages in Indian agriculture. Nearly 54 million people were covered by legal rationing and another 19 million by public distribution in urban areas by 1947 . GOI initiatives for food grain intervention include procurement, buffer stock, public distribution, importations, restrictions on internal food grain movement, export controls, etc. Not all of these acts need to be applied at the same time

. In 1943, the very first food grains Policy Committee, proposed informal rationing in rural areas. In other words, production areas, free or open market for food grains was allowed in rural areas. . Post-independence, it was anticipated that the government will remove the restrictions on

production, distribution, and prices of food grains. The food grains Policy Committee in 1947, suggested a gradual deregulation in the food grains sector resulting in a policy of gradual decontrol being announced by GOI in November 1947 . The eventual anticipation that decontrol would pave a way towards dislocation of stocks, growth in purchases, and price stability could not hold and the prices started to rise rapidly. Consequently, in September 1948, a reversal of controls was agreed.

Following reappearances of controls, purchase of sufficient stocks for public distribution became vital (GOI, 1976, Part I, p. 145). By August 1949, the GOI began receiving complaints about the quality of disseminated food grains, and named the Food Grains Investigation Committee, that presented its report on April 30 1950 corroborating the complaints.

Given the continuing disparity between public procurement and procurement commitments, on the basis of a recommendation of the All India Food Ministers' Conference held in August 1949, a Food grain Procurement Committee was formed on February 08, 1950. The Committee on food grains Procurement of 1950 advocated "monopolies of food grain purchases, the abolition of the free market, imposition of complete statutory rationing in cities of 50 000 and above population, and informal rationing elsewhere" .As the GOI acknowledged that any scheme of decontrol would be risky, on July 8, 1952 the government issued the 1952 order for food grains (licensing and procurement) prohibiting any individual, other than under or under licensing issued by the State Governments, from engaging in any business involving the purchase, selling, or storage of any foodstuffs for sale.

The Essential Commodities Act of 1955 gave the government a mandate to control the production, supply, distribution and exchange of essential commodities for equal distribution . The Committee on Agricultural Prices was set up in January 1965 following a recommendation of the 1964 Food grains Price Committee. The important thing is that the floor or support price recommended by the Committee for 1964-65 for major food grains was "generally higher than the average post-harvest prices during the preceding three seasons" . Thus, the public distribution would not immediately lower the price of producersellers. Indeed, the National Agriculture Commission recognizes "the minimum support price should be fair to the farmer and should cover his cost of production and leave him a reasonable margin of profit"

In order to promote the governance of trade and trade, the Essential Commodity (EC) Act, came into force in 1955. The EC Act of 1955 empowered the public authorities to implement the system

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of public distribution. However, the 1955 Act was not the first to enact trade and distribution restrictions. Of course, in Independent India, it was the first. The UK Colonial Government had adopted certain control steps under the laws of Defence of India. Since 1946, the Critical Supply Act (Temporary Powers) has been in effect and was in turn replaced by the 1955 EC Act (20). According to the Act, the number of goods declared necessary has increased rapidly from 10 items in 1955 to 60 in the year 1992. In August 1992, the EC (Special Provisions) Act was extended for five more years.

A network of FPSs authorized by state/UT administrations in India ensures the supply of grains of food, where each of these shops is intended to serve a population of 2000. The FPS count of more than 4 lakhs in March 1992 as at 31 March 1995 was more than 4.33 lakhs. The bulk of the FPSs are located in rural areas. In 1995, the number of FPSs in rural areas was three-fold more than in urban areas. The purchase of food grain for distribution through PDS is maintained through domestic purchasing rather than imports. The Green Movement of the late 1960s undoubtedly encouraged this. The PDS quickly became the centrepiece of the program against poverty. In line with the ambitious goals of expanding the PDS to cover the entire population - both rural and urban - the large supplies of food grains provided by the Green Revolution. The price of feed grain procured by the government determines the price at which food grains are received by consumers under this system through PDS. From the outset, the GOI has made it clear that pay prices should play an important role in its agricultural policy.

In January 1965, when the GOI created the FCI, the idea of state trading was regenerated by an Act of the Parliament. The FCI and the Agricultural Price Commission (now the Commission for Agrarian Prices and Costs) arrived in 1965 for procurement and price establishment respectively. Thus, institutional arrangements and procedures for the procurement, inventory, the pricing and delivery of food grains were developed in the period after 1965. Let us take a brief survey of how the public delivery system continues and improves its service.

PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM: THE RATIONALE

The social safety net of the public distribution system can be appreciated by the fact that the overall supply of food grains alone is inadequate to guarantee that food grains can be obtained. However, production alone cannot guarantee automatic utilization. The commencement of initial production is an unknown exploratory for human beings. The desire to survive or initial material life forces humans, to alter the surroundings (obtainable and available to him) by the sheer application of his labor. Initial output is produced by an individual regardless of his own choice and independent of

the question of any accord. It is this singular obligation which becomes a social phenomenon because of (i) The inability of the person(s) to produce all the supplies that he/she needs; (ii) The choice-neutrality of any particular individual. The above in particular, cannot satisfy everybody equally in the relative command of individuals over generated resources. Thus, command differential is created over commodities. The difference in commands is based on the difference of resources: unequal resources owned and converted by the owners in the field of commodities output . The corollary is that the mere existence of food in the economy or in the market does not entitle a person to eat food . The poor living in rural areas in revenue poor developing countries as well as the urban poor with insufficient buying power are often denied a right to food, both without a regular job (paid work) and without unemployment benefit.

The use of the right to food and to be hungry is synonymous with such a poor person. Unless an effective distribution system exists, even the ability to buy cannot guarantee food safety. In this study we consider cross-sectional (societal poor protection). As the 10th Planning Commission, the State of India, has confessed: "Food grains are not adequate to guarantee the safety of the poor. The poor must still have enough money to buy food. There are two ways to ensure that the poor are able to afford food—by growing their wages or offering subsidized food grains. Although the first option is attempted by job services, the second alternative is the PDS mechanism”.

India's colonial past also confirms that 'important famines and shortages existed at a time when India was the country surplus food and actually exported large quantities of foodstuffs.' Nationally at least, hunger "was not precipitated in British India by the absolute lack of food caused by uncontrollable natural vagaries". The regulation of the food of the various economic cross-sections of population in an economy depends upon several legal and institutional factors, including governance, political will and competence, goal setting, ownership and control of food, etc. Much like the 1973 food famine in Ethiopia, the 1974 famine in Bangladesh was not linked to decreased availability of food .

In history, there is no causal link between the per capita availability of food and the lack of food consumption by a portion of the population. Food protection and food self-sufficiency are two separate problems, but they are related to a national economy with different parts with and without buying power in the sense of the size of the population. Macro food self-sufficiency (taking the single unit A food economy) is not a guarantee of food safety. Many Asian, African and Latin American countries have significant and rising population numbers. Many are hungry and

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malnourished by this growing scale. It was estimated, for example, that about 100 million people in 1985 or approximately one fourth of the settled population in Africa remained chronically hungry and malnourished. In the mid-1980s, the food import expenditure accounted for some 20.0% of Africa's overall export earnings, compared to 16.0% in 1980 .

An economy must import food if the domestic supply is lower than the demand, while the lack of purchasing power of the lowest segments of the population in the same economy will lead to poverty and malnutrition (23). The challenge is to ensure that the vulnerable segments of the economy remain food secure, even at the expense of food imports. However, the ability to import food has now been limited in a vast economy like India with a population of over 1000 million. In 1989, for example, rice production in India was five times worldwide, while wheat production in India was half worldwide.

India produced 21.2% of world rice production and 10.0% of world wheat production in 1989 (24). For a large economy such as India, the best option is not to rely on food imports to ensure food certainty, as the complete demand for food requirements cannot be met even by joint exported from the rest of the world. This is because the developed countries have moved away from food production while the developing countries essentially grow food to maintain food balance within the domestic economy. Therefore, it is fair for the government to interfere in the system of food production distribution.

At the level of all of the Indian countries, the per capita consumption of cereals dropped from 15,3 kg to 13,4 kg per month during the two decades, according to data from the National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO). During the two decades that ended 1993-94, the food share in all of India has been steadily declining from about 73% to 55%. In all countries, this decrease occurred. The NSSO has estimated that food shares have decreased for the first (poor) quartile for all the income groups, despite the fact that the poor people continue to spend the bulk of their budget on food and even more than the non-poor people spend on food. Engel's Rule, which says economic growth is followed by decreasing food shares, may seem to suggest that. We assume that the reverse is not necessarily true: declining and decreasing food shares mean economic growth. Even if this implies economic growth, the social foundations of this development would be weak and unsustainable. Flexibility in the eating patterns of the - 25 - disadvantaged parts of society can often mask the real reasons why food consumption is reduced. For example, 'reduced consumption of food could be an early answer to the risk of a failure of rights which is apparently at least partially

motivated by protection of productive assets' (22). However, a fall in per capita food intake can be due to changing food composition. The Bennett Law argues that customers increasingly turn to a higher cost diet, which replaces quality with quantity. This has been verified by the NSSO data in the Indian sense.

The decrease in per-capita cereals consumption is wholly due to a drop in coarse cereal consumption, from 4.8 kg to 2 kg per capita per month, between 1972-1973 and 1993- 94. The increase of consumption of wheat from 3.9 kg per month to 4.4 kg per capita was not adequate to offset the decrease of total consumption of cereals. During this time rice consumption remained virtually unchanged. The substitution from coarse cereals to rice, according to the NSSO data, was prominent for lower income classes, and there was hardly any change in rice and wheat consumption in the non-poor parts. The explanation is possibly that the non-poor portion already has enough cereals to satisfy its satiety. Before the poor people's income transition from grain to non-cereal, they move from lower-cost to more costly cereals.

From the Indian perspective, this suggests a change from the coarse cereals to either wheat or rice, or both. PDS has remained an important tool for enforcing the economic policy of the Indian Government to protect the vulnerable. Public interference on the - 26 - food grain market aims to procure food grains for the public distribution and preserve buffer stocks, so that prices of critical commodities are not only stable for a short period of time, but also for a long time and the interests of consumers are safeguarded. Food grain procures would also provide farmers with remuneration and incentives to invest more in agriculture in an effort to increase productivity, ensuring that the market prices do not fall below the support prices in case of any surplus or for any other purpose.

Since the beginning of the 1970s, the Government of India's objective had been to make sure farmers receive their product prices and don't have to do distress sale of their produce, particularly during the harvest season following the policy of the minimum price of support (MSP) (GOI, 1998-99, p.73). As the Government has announced, procurement rates are based on government support prices. The purchasing of wheat, paddy and coarse grain is an entirely voluntary activity. The producers may sell their goods in the open, or on the FCI/State, at support rates to FCI/State agencies (GOI, 1998-99, p. 70). The goal of the PDS is to ensure stability in the food grains market as food grain prices fluctuate less because of constant availability of grains with the government. This reduces scarcity and monitors speculative patterns.

The goal of this PDS is to help the marginalized and deprived parts of society. It also commits to pay close attention to trouble-prone regions, desert zones, tribal zones, urban slum zones and hilly areas. In addition to additional products such as tea, soap, iodized salt and pulse to support the tribal and the village in backwards and remote - 27 - areas, a special program was launched from June 1992 on the strengthening of PDS (GOI, 1994-95, p. 78). Both inadequate infrastructure and income poverty tend to be the causes for this special scheme. Food grains at highly subsidized rates were intended for BPL family members (GUI, 1998-99, p. 69). The government had to import food grains at government-declared prices to carry out PDS and TPDS. The government claimed that food grain procurement was intended to provide farmers with price protection that would allow them to maintain their production levels. It acted as a tool to defend vulnerable segments from market fluctuations as well as PDS.

REVAMPED PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM: SOME FEATURES

The government has initiated measures to reform the PDS to boost its scope based on a region approach, in consultation with state governments and the Union Territory (UT) administrations. The people living in the most difficult regions of the world had to be given priority in this revamped scheme. These include areas that are vulnerable to drought, desert areas, tribal areas, some hilly and urban slum areas. Thus, in June 1992, a revision of the Public Distribution System (RPDS) in 1,700 blocks was introduced. Additional goods such as tea, soap, pulses and iodine salt have been given under the RPDS for tribal, hill and arid communities remotely located and with low infrastructure. The GOI in the mid-1990's determined that the RPDS' geographical scope would be expanded to the whole of the 2,446 Blocks of the Employment Assurance Scheme (G01, - 28 - 1995-96, p. 84). Under RPDS, food grain (rice and wheat) for lower prices is given to the Member States and the union territories; Rs. 50 per quintal is lower than the CIPs for usual PDS blocks.

States Governments are expected to ensure that these products' retail prices are not higher by more than 25 countries per kg in these blocks than CIPs. Sugar is also available at lower prices (GOI, 1992-93, p. 90). The Central Government for PDS as well as RPDS is developing CIPs (ex-FCI godowns). State Governments shall set the retail prices for PDS and RPDS considering the cost of transport and the fee of the dealer (G01, 1995-96, p.87). The difference between the PDS and the RPDS in terms of retail price is that for RPDS, the central government has set a maximum limit of

Rs. 25 for each quintal on the basis of transport cost, etc (G01, 1995-96, p. 87). Four significant deficiencies have been found by the program assessment agency of the Planning Committee. These include (i) the proliferation of bogus cards, ii) insufficient storage arrangements, iii) the failure of the vigilance committee to work effectively and iv) failure of all qualifying homes to issue ration cards .

FEATURES OF THE TARGETED PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM

In order to achieve 'transitory allocation' for the state the quantity of food grains exceeding the requirement of the BPL families were allocated to 103 lakh of food grains per year. In addition to the TPDS allocation, the States were also granted additional - 29 - allocations. The transitory allocation was intended to continue to support the population of APL from the subsidized food grains because sudden removal of PDS benefits from the subsidies was deemed unwelcome. The temporary assignment was made at subsidized prices but higher than the BPL quota prices of food grain. Therefore, from June 1997, the TPDS replaced the former PDS. The scheme split potentials into the BPL and APL. The Government has undertaken to spread 10 kg under the TPDS. Food grains per BPL family month at a price equivalent to half the FCI's economic expense. An approximate 6 crores population received 72 lakh tons of foodstuffs per year to meet BPL requirements. The Planning Committee of Lakdawala described the number of poor people in each country. The States were responsible for recognizing the disadvantaged.

The impetus was only on the inclusion of poor and marginalized parts of society, such as landless farm workers, marginalized farmers, rural craftsmen and slum dwellers and the day-to-day waging of the informal sector in urban areas. State authorities were given the task of rationalizing PDS, with better oversight, by supplying BPL families with special cards and distributing necessary goods to them at specially subsidized rates under the TPDS. The States had been granted the right to bifurcate food grain and APL quotas into rice and wheat. The average lifting of rice and wheat over the last ten years was taken on a provisional basis for those States which did not indicate the bifurcation. Under the TPDS guidelines any demand from states outside the TPDS quota may be - 30 - met at rates equal to the average economic cost of the FCI (GOI 1997-98, p. 72) subject to the availability of food grains in the Central Pool. In order to achieve 'transitory allocation' for the state

the quantity of food grains exceeding the requirement of the BPL families were allocated to 103 lakh of food grains per year. In addition to the TPDS allocation, the States were also granted additional allocations. The transitory allocation was intended to continue to support the population of Above the Poverty Line (APL) from the subsidized food grains because sudden removal of PDS benefits from the subsidies was deemed unwelcome. The temporary assignment was made at subsidized prices but higher than the BPL quota prices of food grains.

With the agreement that food grains should be distributed more to BPL families and that food subsidies should be better targeted, the Indian government raised BPL family allocations by ten kilograms at an economic cost of up to 20 kg of food grains per family a month at 50% of APL families cost and allocation. The Allocation of the APL families was preserved at the same level as that at the time of the implementation of the TPDS, but the Central Issue Prices (CIP) for APL had been set at 100% for the economic cost since that date, so that the entire market subsidy could be charged for the benefit of the BPL public. However, since that date, while procurement costs have risen substantially, the CIPs set for BPL& AAY in July and December 2000 and for AIP in July 2002 have not been revised. - 31 - Since 1.12.2000 the forecast for the number of BPL families has substantially increased, by changing the population projections of the Registrar General as on 1.3.2000. As opposed to 596,23 lakh families originally estimated when TPDS was introduced in June 1997, the total number of BPL families increased to 652,03 lakhs. After considering wholesale / retailer margins, transport charges, levies, local tax, etc the final retail prices are determined by the states/UT. As part of TPDS it was requested to the States to food grains to BPL families at price differences not exceeding 50 paise/kg above the CIP. The states/UTs have been given the freedom to fix retail prices with the removal of a restriction to the distribution of food grain by 50 paise/kg, over and above CIP, under the TPDS except in the case of AAY where the final prices shall be kept at Rupees 2/kg. For Rupees 3/kg of wheat and rice, respectively

OPERATIONS, FOOD CORPORATION OF INDIA

As of 2018 there were 21,847 employees working in FCI

The Food Corporation of India procures rice and wheat from farmers through many routes like paddy purchase centres/mill levy/custom milling and stores them in depots. FCI maintains many types of depots like food storage depots and buffer storage complexes and private equity godowns and also implemented latest storage methods of silo storage facilities which are located at Hapur in Uttar Pradesh, Malur in Karnataka and Elavur in Tamil Nadu.

In order to achieve the food security of the Uttar Pradesh, the Sales Division of FCI Regional office Lucknow looks after one of the most important operation i.e. distribution of food grains under TPDS & Other Welfare Schemes.

Government of India fulfills the objectives of food security through the Public Distribution System. Public Distribution System strives to meet the twin objectives of price support to the farmers for their product and supply of foodgrains at affordable prices. It is against the stocks procured under price support, Government releases a certain quantity of foodgrains in each State under the Public Distribution System. This mission of the Government of India is translated into reality by the FCI. In order to implement the food policy of Government, FCI has to fulfil certain objectives which are as follows:

1. To ensure and equitable distribution of available foodgrains at reasonable prices to the vulnerable sections of society throughout the year;
2. To maintain stability in foodgrains prices throughout country during the year;
3. To maintain an adequate buffer stock of foodgrains to deal with fluctuations in production and to meet unforeseen exigencies and natural calamities.

.The Government of India fulfills certain objectives of food security through Public Distribution at an affordable price. In the present scenario, Public Distribution System strives to meet the twin objectives - the price support to the farmers for their product and maintenance of stocks. It is against these stocks procured under price support that every month Government releases a prescribed quantity, in each State for distribution under Public Distribution System. This mission of the Government of India is brought into the reality at the operational level by FCI. The Sales Division communicates the said allocation to its Regional Offices. On receipt of sub-allocation from the State Government, the Regional Offices Lucknow issue the instructions to the District Offices for releasing the stocks to the UP State Government /their nominees on prepayment basis at district level.

Targeted Public Distribution System (T.P.D.S.)

Public Distribution System was widely criticized for its failure to serve the population below the poverty line, its urban bias, negligible coverage in the States with the highest concentration of the

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rural poor and lack of transport and accountable arrangements for delivery. Realizing this, the Government of India introduced the TPDS scheme w.e.f. 1.6.1997 (w.e.f. 1.5.1997 for the states of Tripura, Haryana and Gujarat) to streamline the PDS by issuing special cards to the families below the poverty line (BPL) and selling essential articles under PDS to them at a specially subsidized prices with better monitoring of the delivery system. The families belonging to above the poverty line were categories as APL families.

During the year 2000, Government of India decided to issue rice and wheat at the rate of Rs. 3/- per Kg. And Rs. 2/- per Kg., respectively to the poorest of the poor population out of the earlier identified BPL population and were categories as Antyodaya families. Hence, w.e.f. the year 2000, the TPDS has three categories of families viz. APL, BPL, and AAY families. There are different category-wise Central Issue Prices under TPDS.

Government Schemes

Schemes	Year Introduced	Coverage Target Group	Latest Volume	Issue Price (Rs Per Kg)
Public Distribution System (PDS)	Upto 1992	Universal	N/A	Wheat:2.34 Rice :2.89
Revamped Public Distribution System (RPDS)	1992	Backward Blocks	20 kg of food grains	Wheat:2.80 Rice:3.77
Targeted Public Distribution System (TPDS)	1997	Poor and Non-Poor BPL APL	35 kg of food grains	BPL – <u>Wheat</u> -4.15 <u>Rice</u> -5.65 APL - <u>Wheat</u> -6.10 <u>Rice</u> -8.30
Antyodaya Anna Yojana	2000	Poorest of the poor	35 kg of food grains	Wheat:2.00 Rice:3.00
Annapurna Scheme	2000	Indigent Senior Citizens	10 kg of food grains	free

National Food Security Act,2013	2013	Priority Households	5 kg per person per month	Wheat:2.00 Rice :3.00 Millet:1.00 Sugar :5.00
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Role of FCI in PDS

The role of Food Corporation of India is to ensure supply of foodgrains to the States as per the allotment made by the Government of India at the applicable Central Issue Prices. The stock of foodgrains under PDS is issued through joint sampling method. Further, FCI has no control over the stock once lifted and taken out of FCI premises.

The responsibility of distributing the foodgrains to the targeted beneficiaries through Fair Price Shops rests with the respective Uttar Pradesh State Government.

Pricing

The Government of India, Ministry of CA,F&PD has been fixing Central Issue Prices of wheat and rice from time to time which is uniform throughout the country. The present Central Issue price of wheat and rice are as under:-

(Rate:Rs/Quintal)

Commodity	PHH	AAY
Wheat	200	200
Rice	300	300

Validity

Government of India is allocating foodgrains (wheat and rice) under Targeted Public Distribution System on monthly basis and issues allocation order for the financial-year wise and makes further revision, if any, from time to time.

Ministry during 28th July 2014 has revised the instructions to streamlining of procedure regarding issuance and revalidation/extension of validity period for lifting of foodgrains under TPDS. The

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validity period for lifting of allocated foodgrains under TPDS will be 30 days for each allocation month separately, starting from 1st day of the month preceding the allocation month and ending on last day of the month preceding the allocation month. For example, the validity period for the allocation for April will be from 1st March to 31st March.

Ministry has made it mandatory for State and UT Government to deposit the cost of foodgrains to FCI so much in advance so that the lifting is completed by end of the previous month. Further, power delegated for extension of 15 days each by General Manager (Region) & Executive Director(Zone), FCI, both for depositing cost and lifting of foodgrains shall continue. For the period beyond 30 days after the prescribed validity period, the matter will have to be referred to the Ministry by the concerned State/UTs

LATEST TRENDS IN PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM

Aadhaar as an identifier:

People belonging to marginalized sections of the society often do not have a valid proof of identity. As a result, they miss out on availing social benefits provided by the government. Aadhaar has been successful in solving this problem.

One of the quintessential properties of Aadhaar is its uniqueness. It is an identification that a person can carry for a life time and potentially use with any service provider thus, fundamentally becoming a pro-poor identification infrastructure.

It provides a single view of beneficiary data and information, aiding in streamlining policy decisions for the state

Social Benefit Delivery Services:

Enables State Governments to directly transfer benefits to beneficiary accounts under various schemes.

Beneficiary Identification:

Helps in sanitizing the State's/Department's databases and uniquely identifying beneficiaries by removing ghost/duplicate identities

Demographic and development planning: Enables valuable anonymized demographic data to help development planning at State, District and local government levels.

Preventing leakages:

Welfare programs, where beneficiaries need to be confirmed before service delivery, also stand to benefit from UIDAI's verification service.

Examples of such usages include subsidized food and kerosene delivery to Public Distribution System (PDS) beneficiaries.

This usage would ensure that services are delivered to the right beneficiaries only.

Challenges

However, the use of Aadhaar-based biometric authentication (ABBA) in the public distribution system has its own share of challenges:

- ABBA requires not only Aadhaar seeding, but also successful fingerprint authentication at the ration shop every month. That, in turn, requires a functional Point of Sale (PoS) machine, adequate connectivity, and reasonably smooth fingers. Despite some alleged safeguards, the system is far from perfect
- Evidence from Jharkhand suggests that ABBA is of little use in reducing PDS corruption.
- Neither seeding nor the ABBA can stop quantity fraud.
- If PDS dealers give people less than their due, biometric authentication does not help.
- Cases of deaths due to hunger as people could not collect rations because of a biometric mismatch at the PDS shop.
- Disenfranchisement of the elderly and the disabled, as ABBA requires beneficiaries to visit the PDS outlet personally for fingerprint authentication.
- **Seeding issues:**
- When benefits are paid through Aadhaar-enabled means such as the Aadhaar Payments Bridge System (APBS), the first step is to seed the list of beneficiaries with the corresponding Aadhaar numbers. Seeding is a tedious operation and it has to be done each time a new scheme is inducted. Those who have failed to comply are simply removed from the lists
- Seeding often creates inconsistencies between ration-cards database and the Aadhaar database.
- Many poor people do not know the rules of Aadhaar seeding and biometric authentication.

Inclusion errors increase the financial burden of the state, exclusion errors can often leave poor families vulnerable to hunger.

Deprivation of poor:

- Poor people often find themselves deprived of their rights in the process. For instance, linking one's pension or ration card or bank account with Aadhaar is a tedious process as data-entry errors are common.
- And even without such errors, Aadhaar linking often fails because a person's demographic details in the Aadhaar database do not match the corresponding details in her job card or ration card

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- The government failed to address these issues as job cards, ration cards and pensions have been mass-cancelled in many states.

Many poor people do not know the rules of Aadhaar seeding and biometric authentication.

Inclusion errors increase the financial burden of the state, exclusion errors can often leave poor families vulnerable to hunger.

Deprivation of poor:

Poor people often find themselves deprived of their rights in the process. For instance, linking one's pension or ration card or bank account with Aadhaar is a tedious process as data-entry errors are common.

And even without such errors, Aadhaar linking often fails because a person's demographic details in the Aadhaar database do not match the corresponding details in her job card or ration card.

The government failed to address these issues as job cards, ration cards and pensions have been mass-cancelled in many states.

Way forward

- Inconsistencies need to be resolved for successful Aadhaar seeding.
- It is essential to deal with issues of duplication, use less disruptive methods than Aadhaar such as food coupons, smart cards, and last-mile tracking
- Using other technology to curb corruption like computerisation, SMS alerts, online availability of official records, toll-free help lines and so on.
- It is imperative that the Union Government enact a privacy legislation that clearly defines the rights of citizens consistent with the promise of the Constitution.
- The government should factor in privacy risks and include procedures and systems to protect citizen information in any system of data collection. It should create institutional mechanism such as Privacy Commissioner to prevent unauthorised disclosure of or access to such data.
- Our national cyber cell should be made well capable of dealing with any cyber attack in shortest time.

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